

Emotions by Products in Cultural Contexts

Leonardo Springer, IADE University, Lisbon – Portugal

Abstract

In a context of slowing down the pace and total integration of the design process, one must think in the introduction of new ways of delivering current items and products for a broader consumer. These products become thus bearers of collective emotions and symbols of social amalgamation, reeling on basic interpretations, common to us all as humans.

Cross cultural design aspects bare upon non-verbal communication such as play, a basic learning process and a key element in the design-driven process.

Through innovation and sustained design, cultural aspects can improve creative design response in multifarious design interfaces.

This paper describes research aimed to qualify the cultural transfer in the design discipline, where small detail provides a homogenous understanding of interface and product design.

Keywords: Cross-culture; Discovery; Play; Interaction; Maieutic; Sintropy; Fast Interfaces.

Introduction

Products are created to serve a purpose - the consumer's purpose.

Emotions differ from one culture to another; hence products often don't have the same aspect to different users in different countries. A good example of this, are the different cooking's eating that differ from one culture to another depending on issues as varied as climate and technology.

We discover that our needs change in the most prolific cultures those that we access with a double click, one that that is not ours, our culture vanishes in a more and more global world and as human beings, we distinguish ourselves with a culture that is familiar to us - home. In an overcrowded planet, by consumer products and services, the individual expression is overruled, what is there left for the designer in the ethical, social and moral stand?

The system is based in client satisfaction, however consumer industry provides Man with objects he has no desire nor need for, artefacts have different filters, as a designer is trained to provide solutions.

A rupture with precepts and predefined schemes is urgent, it is necessary to question the present design development process, and thus creating new artefacts need to put the essence of Man and it's cultural contexts in the core of the design process. Thus do cultural contexts have a consequence on the design process?

Play Element in Design

One of the important goals of emotion-driven design is to transcend instrumental benefits of products and to facilitate an experience such as play, valuable by itself. Play is an internally motivated activity that all humans engage in some form from time to time, by integrating these elements into products they enrich their engaging experience and inspire the user and co-user within a certain context minimising error in employment.

Objects like a pen or writing element are prone to be found all over the globe, verbal and iconographic messages are part of our everyday lives, and contributions that evaluate and discuss concrete examples address the role of the play element in design. Within a certain cultural context, play can overcome comprehension difficulties and minimise error of use, on the other hand humour can present lack of understanding because of the use a specific language. The global design process presents various forms of play elements, these can have inconveniences when used incorrectly, and there is therefore a need to rule out misleading elements when potential danger of comprehension is acknowledged.

Figure 1, visual incoherence used as a play symbol.

Emotions within a Cultural Context

Do emotional responses of consumers differ from one cultural context to another? Most certainly, depending on various factors, these emotions universes are specific to a culture, or cultural context, and to an individual. Different research has been done implicating that neurological constraints, small changes in the blood pressure; muscle tone and facial appearance imply different results, also known as emotions. But as this is true, than the difference of race, gender and culture become self-evident, as differences themselves, thus perception of environs is a memory of past experiences.

Each culture has symbols and icons, which elicit favourable emotions shared by a group within society; culture is therefore a mixture of Human experiences and collective emotions. Certain (types of) objects, crafts and products within different cultures, artefacts that give specific meaning to that group as a football scarf to the fan group, becoming bearers of collective emotions and symbols of social integration, as the “Portuguese galo de Barcelos” is a icon and a cultural reference of Portuguese folklore.

Figure 2, Portuguese “Galo de Barcelos“ a cultural folklore icon.

Cultures create artefacts and these by its own process create culture, values, concepts, and performance of interactive systems are part of the cultural life cycle and need to become part of the design process in a conscious manner. Humans are skilful in detecting alteration in the surroundings, to understand cause and purpose, seek reason and justify the cultural background. Every cultural aspect is an explanation based on the concept of culture as a network of meanings woven by human beings in societies - context, where they develop their

behaviour, and through which they give meaning to their own individual lives. The *habitus* concept of Bourdieu entails that human beings interact with specific structures in the external world

The *habitus* is constituted through the past experiences, both individual and collective, of subjects within the world. Therefore, the habitual modes of thought licensed by the *habitus* are based upon experiences of social practices and not upon an inquiry into what is true (Bourdieu, P., 1980).

From this point of view, it assumes that interpretation can vary in communication, according to each particular culture of individuals and societies. Furthermore, it considers that human beings don't perceive things as isolated elements, without relation between them, but organise them during the perception process.

The development of a cultural concept evolves from taken values in a specific context, whereas it comes from the cognitive knowledge from an iconic representation or from iteration with a system, humans have become the product of their culture, and the routine with the system is part of the artefacts life cycle.

Effect on the Design process

Nowadays, as designers tend to team up with different areas and broaden their studies to cope with an ever-demanding industry, understanding of cultural aspects and users in a specific or broaden context is critical to meet the expectations and needs for an accurate communication. The designer must ask himself, during the process, in what context is the user handling the product and what cultural aspects are relevant to the product development?

Cultural issues affect global business in three critical areas: 1) a company's own internal cultures, working in cross-cultural and inter-disciplinary teams, 2) producing products and services for users with diverse needs, values and habits, 3) managing brand in different cultures that will have different Interpretations of a company's behaviour and presence (...)
(Whitney, P. 2001, pp18-19).

The non-stopping development is based in transforming inputs into outputs, with several assessment tools such as: observation, product analysis and development, social implication,

user interface, SWOT analysis, client satisfaction, it is a complex labour. In addition, design has turned into a global and multi-disciplined process where different cultures mingle in multinational design studios in different parts of the globe, also by using a set of different technologies the output is necessarily different affecting the process as a whole.

The products need of safety, namely of fast use and fool proof (undo button), is a procedure that dictates success or failure of new products, where considering the user's possibility to smoothly assimilate new products by given custom habits, expectations, or general ways of behaviour in a given cultural context.

So what are the significant factors for a rapid reading and use?

The design in different cultural contexts implies new affordances, new inclusiveness with new emotional readings to reach all of the potential users. Designers face today the challenge of combining technologies (that develops at an incredible rate) with new product concepts based on user needs, activities and emotional readings in order to innovate successfully, designating the scope of product development within a given context.

Almost all of today's interfaces are designed assuming that they will be the centre of our attention, however attention is a scarce resource, as we are bombarded with more and more information streams, we can no longer assume that we will devote all of our attention to any one thing. As the numbers of applications and artefacts that we engage with on a typical day continues to increase, the limits of human attention remain the same.

How can one perceive an interface, designed to perform a function with a different aesthetic within a different culture? To understand this ever-growing problem, how does a design interface support the demands and limitations of human attention, one must understand the variety of contexts for instance, work, leisure, and mobility have different concentration demands and attention span. The information acquired interacts on the function of attention, short-term memory, visual short-term memory, the auditory loop, and visual principles, all of them captured and activated by our sensibility and emotional state, dependant on our cultural context (a gunshot in Gaza strip and on a small Greek island) can be worlds apart mattering what is considered normal. The real power of interface design resides in the interaction itself, analogical or digital, that can be used to communicate context and meaning relating to a

previously known emotion, apprehended and identified in a past, whereas with a different artefact or one that resembles the fist, physically or in procedure.

The answer is that the physical design of an object makes all the difference. You can often tell by the just by looking at something what function it serves or, at least, which parts you are supposed to hold push, or pull, which parts operate on other devices (Donald A. Norman, 2004).

A society with limited resources develops its affordance, much is developed in order to comply with needs improvising and adapting existing artefacts rather than designing custom made products. What people perceive the object can do, the object's possible use, with its shape, size, weight, etc., is the object's real end use, if proper training hasn't been given the artefact will be used in a different manner from the one designed for. The real use must be foreseen to the broadest spectrum during the usage and considered during design process.

Figure 3, Lever action, what is the right movement.

Many solutions are already on the market but the awareness of these products hasn't yet been broadly used to promote good design interface, one, that uses cognitive knowledge and emotive reaction as a use facilitator. The development in design of icons (cultural products or spaces) contributes in the formation, reproduction and transformation of values, and the relations and practices of society itself.

Figure 5, Exit or not? Red means Stop

Understanding context of use is essential to human-centred design and innovation, users, contexts and products together create user experience and emotions resulting in a response and understanding the artefact in it's context of use, essential to human-cantered design contexts and products together create user experience and thus procedure of operation memorized in the future.

Users refer as good design something that is convenient, aesthetically pleasing, easy to clean, cheap, benign, environmentally friendly and time saving to name a few of the known. Cultures diverge in so many aspects that the design outcome is necessarily different, however multinational companies have bombarded cultures with their own culture, as the HSBC bank promoting itself with an insight considering cultural aspects of different markets.

Figure 6, Campaign to promote differences in custom service (HSBC - 2003)

Customisation or cultural adapted interfaces, artefacts, mechanisms or spaces are complex contexts for assessment; and a context methodology systematically incorporates context into the design of artefacts, managing it to enhance the system performance and user experience

would be a plus. The understanding and systematic incorporation of this concept of cultural contexts in design could lead to new errors but could also lay the foundation for the development and reconfiguration of interface, artefacts and space, acting as a facilitator and customizing different uses in addition of empowering the final user.

Emotion, Experience and Expressivities

Interaction designers are concerned with designing product dialogues using context to engage people in user-product interactions and to create emotions and evoke experiences. To understand there is a need to identify cultural and emotional context of product design, and how this might change the behavioural and even social aspects of the individuals that interact with it. This is a long-term analysis, the time span of a generation, as objects can have different meaning from fathers to sons in addition of cultural contexts.

Of all affective states or experiences, the emotional experience is the most relevant for understanding product experience because only emotions imply a one-to-one relationship between the experience and the object (Desmet & Hekkert, 2001).

As people become more sensitive to the dimensions of products that go beyond traditional aspects of usability, their need to understand and create emotional and aesthetic significance increases. Issues of emotion, affective response, and inclusive human concerns are exceedingly important in design for emotional context of message remains in sight at all times regardless of the type of information being presented.

However, designers lack a shared understanding and language for emotion within the context of design. While each discipline brings its own theories of emotion to the design process, these theories need to be understood and integrated so as to enrich rather than obstruct collaborative design activity.

Conclusions

Design, is the discipline of creating and making something perform a function, hence that is deliberately and consciously created is a design process and often the designer's job is to influence consumers to have certain feelings or emotions. For the past decade "think globally,

act locally” has been a good example of global culture, defending local communities and their interests to the global market’s production. One must take into account that global business has become standard but local methods and cultures have its own methodology, and outputs. Products that have this objective belong somewhere between icons and good products.

Figure 4, Cultural driven design process.

Along the design process the designer makes a number of options and decisions within the project forgetting sometimes to observe the humans behind the task, good design should always be human centred, one should not incur in the error of designing artefacts that by having good metaphors and semantic values by not indulging the function of the end user. These theories of human emotion resources are cultural tools (within a context) as the play element is in the learning process, it is also a tool that can be used to let the end user learn its interaction process and evolve to use and transform the act itself into assimilated cognitive knowledge with the artefact, giving a new meaning to the last.

Training highly skilled professionals useful to society such as designers commonly draw upon: social science, material science cognitive science, and aesthetics to bridge issues to an outcome. The analysis of emotional interactions within a different cultural context makes possible the development of a design process for different locations and users, these would have a beneficial employment outcome and significant improvements to the efficiency and effectiveness of designers working for different markets. Further more that this combination of relationships affects perceptions of the individual and collective within different society, through participation or interaction in their cultural setting.

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Leonardos Springer has a background in industrial design from IADE University - Lisbon, where he has been teaching since 1999, he is also involved in research at the IN+ Centre for Innovation, Technology and Policy - Technical University of Lisbon. He obtained an MA in industrial design from Central Saint Martins – London in research and development of urban sports equipment. He currently teaches in the areas of Product Development, 3D Modeling and Design, with a wide range of interests he is currently preparing his Phd in the subject of emotions and design. He is also a consultant to several furniture design firms and has been involved in several projects.